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Spirituality and Adult Mental Health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Adults face challenges worldwide that test their psychological strength and coping abilities. This study examines the influence of spirituality on adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria. It focuses on three dimensions of spirituality: spiritual practices, values and ethics, and personal growth and self-reflection. Adult mental health was assessed using resilience and coping, self-esteem and self-worth, and trauma and post-traumatic growth. The study is grounded in logotherapy and resilience theories. Data were collected using a self-developed four-point Likert-scale questionnaire titled *Spirituality and Adult Mental Health (SAMH)*, adapted from established psychological scales. Taro Yamane's formula determined the sample size from a population of 440,400. Four hundred respondents were selected through simple random sampling, and 280 (70%) valid responses were used for analysis. Results showed that spirituality explains 97.5% of the variance in adult mental health, as indicated by the correlation coefficient ($R = .987$) and the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .975$), revealing a very strong predictive relationship. This relationship is statistically significant ($F = 10,714.156$, $p = .000$), and the regression coefficient ($B = .976$, $p = .000$) confirms that spirituality has a

strong positive influence on adult mental health. The study concluded that adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria have high mental health and moderate spirituality, with spirituality significantly predicting and positively influencing mental well-being. It recommends incorporating spiritual values into therapy and mental health programs to enhance adult psychological resilience and overall mental health.

Keywords: Spirituality, Adult Mental Health, Resilience, Post-traumatic Growth, Spiritual Practices

Introduction

As people deal with difficult life transitions, personal obligations, social expectations, and the aftereffects of earlier events, adult mental health has grown in importance on a global scale. Adults encounter difficulties that put their psychological fortitude and coping skills to the test in many parts of the world (Potgieter & Ferreira, 2022). Maintaining mental health frequently depends on things like self-worth, self-esteem, and the ability to bounce back from or even develop after trauma—a process now known as post-traumatic growth (Pandey & Gupta, 2025). Adults who can adjust to hardship and figure out how to make sense of their problems with support from effective social support systems, likely have better mental health outcomes regardless of cultural background (Oyewale, 2024). These processes are rarely linear and are frequently impacted by both external social circumstances and interior belief systems. The inner resources people use to manage, such as identity, meaning-making, and emotional balance, are crucial, even though access to mental health resources varies globally.

These same processes are evident in Nigeria, although they are frequently influenced by particular social, cultural, and economic circumstances. Adults in Nigeria, particularly those living in urban and semi-urban areas, face a lot of pressure from social expectations, family obligations, and unstable economies. However, many people struggle in secret or look for other sorts of emotional assistance because mental health is still not widely recognised or publicly acknowledged (Prizeman et al, 2024). The ideas of resilience and self-worth frequently assume a collective aspect, shaped by social ideals, religious convictions, and familial arrangements. Trauma, whether from individual loss, adversity, or group events, can significantly impact the mental health of many Nigerian adults (Stevenson et al., 2024). At the same time, there is a slow but increasing recognition that mental

health issues need to be addressed and that psychological wellness is essential to leading a successful and satisfying life.

The association between mental health and sociocultural life becomes even more complex when one looks more closely at Ibadan North Local Government Area in Oyo State. As an urban area with a vibrant educational scene, Ibadan North Local Government Area in Oyo State offers adults both possibilities and challenges. People try to balance their family responsibilities, financial obligations, and professional goals while battling the implicit and occasionally explicit expectations of both traditional and contemporary Nigerian culture. In such a setting, narratives about success, failure, perseverance, and emotional expression within the larger community have an impact on mental health in addition to individual situations. Despite their existence, formal mental health treatments are frequently underutilised or seen as a last resort. In light of this, it is crucial to investigate additional factors that may affect how individuals preserve or regain mental health in the face of life's challenges.

Spirituality is among these factors. Examining spirituality as a possible influence on adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria is the aim of this study. Spirituality, despite occasionally overlapping with religion, is typically experienced more generally as a personal and evolving journey (Gschwandtner, 2021). It may involve spiritual practices such as prayer, meditation, or participation in faith-based activities (Haidar et al, 2023). It can also show up in the ethics and values people choose to live by, which can influence how they see other people and themselves (Rietveld & Hoogendoorn, 2022). The search for purpose and personal development, a sense of belonging to a spiritual group, or a connection to a higher force are all sources of strength and emotional stability for many adults (Ukpo et al, 2024). However, three facets of spirituality are explicitly highlighted in this study: individuals' unique spiritual practices, the ethics and values they choose to live by, and their personal growth and self-reflection. These aspects might act as internal tools that support people in finding psychological equilibrium, coping, and resilience during trying situations. This study intends to investigate these connections to determine whether and how spirituality benefits the mental health of individuals in terms of resilience and coping, self-esteem and self-worth, and trauma and post-traumatic growth in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Although adult mental health issues are becoming more widely recognised, many Nigerians still struggle psychologically without the proper help or coping skills. Adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria likely deal with stressors like financial difficulties, familial demands, unresolved trauma, and restricted access to expert mental health services. Some likely suffer from poor self-esteem, emotional anguish, and a lower feeling of self-worth, while others can adjust, and function. Many people turn inside and look to spiritual practices and beliefs for strength and purpose when there are no accessible mental health solutions (Pastwa-Wojciechowska, 2021). Nevertheless, little is known about the precise ways in which spirituality affects adult mental health in this setting. The ways in which self-reflection, accepted values and ethics, and personal spiritual practices may support post-traumatic growth, self-esteem and self-worth, and resilience and coping among adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria are not well understood empirically. Due to this disparity, it is challenging to determine whether spirituality has a positive impact on mental health or if its effects are more complex. To better comprehend spirituality's potential as a protective or enhancing component in adult psychological well-being, it is necessary to look into the relationship between spirituality and adult mental health in this context.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study aims to investigate the influence of spirituality on adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

The objectives of the study are:

1. To determine the level of adult mental health (resilience and coping, self-esteem and self-worth, trauma and post-traumatic growth) in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.
2. To determine the level of spirituality (spiritual practices, values and ethics, personal growth and self-reflection) among adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.
3. To determine if there is a significant relationship between spirituality and adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of adult mental health (resilience and coping, self-esteem and self-worth, trauma and post-traumatic growth) in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of spirituality (spiritual practices, values and ethics, personal growth and self-reflection) among adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between spirituality (spiritual practices, values and ethics, personal growth and self-reflection) and adult mental health (resilience and coping, self-esteem and self-worth, trauma and post-traumatic growth) in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research design of the survey type, which gathers data from a representative sample of the population, to obtain findings that may be applied to the entire population (Taherdoost, 2021). This design's goal is to collect and evaluate data without altering any of the variables.

At the time of this study, Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria records a population of 440,400 (City Population, 2025). Using the Taro Yamane formula $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$, where N is the total population and e is 0.05% level of significance, the study's sample size was determined. The simple random sampling technique was used to select the study's 400 respondents.

A self-developed four-Likert scaled instrument titled Spirituality and Adult Mental Health (SAMH) adapted from notable psychological scales was the instrument for data collection. The instrument is divided into three sections; A, B, and C. Section A includes items on demographics such as respondents' age, gender, and religion. Section B includes 6 items that helped to determine the level of adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria such that items 1-2 measured resilience and coping, items 3-4 measured self-esteem and self-worth, and items 5-6 measured trauma and post-traumatic growth. Similarly, Section C includes 6 items that helped to determine the level of spirituality among

adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria such that items 1-2 measured spiritual practices, items 3-4 measured values and ethics that individuals abide by, and items 5-6 measured personal growth and self-reflection of respondents. The instrument was validated by research experts to ensure that the items in the instruments align with the objectives of the study. All corrections and recommendations were made before the instrument was administered. A pilot research was carried out in Ibadan North East Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. 50 copies of the instrument were completed by respondents who were not included in the actual research. The result confirmed the reliability of the instrument with a Cronbach alpha coefficient of $\alpha = 0.899$. Recognising the individualised nature of spirituality and mental health, the study protected participants' rights, dignity, and well-being throughout the research process by ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, cultural sensitivity, and secure data processing.

Theoretical Framework

Resilience Theory

Norman Garmezy and Emmy Werner created resilience theory, which Ann Masten later developed. It highlights both internal and environmental protective elements that promote mental health and describes how people adjust constructively in the face of hardship, stress, or tragedy (Zalli, 2024). According to this study, spirituality is regarded as a potential resilience component that could support post-traumatic growth, improve self-worth, and help adults in Ibadan North deal with emotional difficulties.

Logotherapy

The foundation of Viktor Frankl's logotherapy is the notion that the pursuit of meaning, even in the midst of suffering, is the fundamental human impulse (Bull, 2024). It emphasises how self-reflection, purpose, and personal values all contribute to psychological well-being. By presenting spirituality—as demonstrated by ethics and values, spiritual practices, and personal growth and self-reflection—as a source of meaning that could improve adult mental health, this theory lends credence to the research.

Literature Review

Concern over adult mental health is on the rise worldwide as people deal with difficult emotional, social, and financial situations that frequently call for resilience, a positive sense of self, and the ability to bounce back from trauma. Since many adults in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria, likely deal with stressors like financial strain and social pressure, it is crucial to investigate mental health topics like coping mechanisms and resilience, self-worth and self-esteem, trauma, and post-traumatic growth in this local setting (Gbadegesin & Ikwuyatum, 2024). The ability to adjust to stress, bounce back from hardship, and keep emotional equilibrium when confronted with life's obstacles is referred to as resilience and coping (Zalli, 2024). People's perceptions of their values and capabilities are reflected in their self-esteem and self-worth, which impact how they handle difficulties, interact with others, and preserve their general psychological health (Cheng et al, 2022). The psychological effects of upsetting events and the possibility that people may discover greater significance, resilience, and personal growth as they heal from them are the subjects of trauma and post-traumatic growth (Ìme et al., 2025). This study examines the influence of spirituality on adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria with a particular emphasis on spiritual practices, values and ethics, personal growth, and self-reflection.

How people look for meaning, connect with a higher power, practice religion or spirituality, and discover a feeling of purpose, belonging, and moral guidance is greatly influenced by spirituality on a local and global level (Long et al, 2024). This study focuses on the ways that three aspects of spirituality; spiritual practices, personal values and ethics, as well as personal growth and self-reflection, influence adult mental health in the cultural context of Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, where spirituality is still a deeply ingrained part of daily life. Spiritual practices, such as prayer, yoga, meditation, worship, fasting, and other faith-based routines, serve as regular expressions of one's beliefs and can provide structure, comfort, and inner strength in times of emotional or psychological distress (Allen et al, 2021). Values and ethics are the moral standards and tenets that people uphold which are frequently influenced by spiritual beliefs and have an impact on people's decisions, actions, and feelings of integrity and purpose in general (Afrilsah, 2024). To become more self-

aware and emotionally mature, people evaluate their values, behaviours, and experiences as part of a continuous process of introspection and self-improvement known as personal growth and self-reflection (Sagiv & Schwartz, 2022). This study emphasises the need for culturally sensitive interventions that incorporate spiritual dimensions to promote mental well-being and emphasises the importance of viewing spirituality as a crucial part of holistic adult mental health care in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Findings

Using the Taro Yamane formula $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$, 400 male and female respondents made up the sample size of the study. However, only 280 (70%) of the administered questionnaires were recovered and deemed suitable for data analysis.

Table A: Gender of Respondents

Gender

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	120	42.9	42.9	42.9
	Female	160	57.1	57.1	100.0
	Total	280	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Table A shows that out of 280 respondents in the study on spirituality and adult mental health in Ibadan North Local Government Area, Oyo State, Nigeria, 42.9% were male (120 respondents) and 57.1% were female (160 respondents).

Table B: Age of Respondents

Age

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-35 years	139	49.6	49.6	49.6
	36-55 years	115	41.1	41.1	90.7
	56 years and Above	26	9.3	9.3	100.0
	Total	280	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researchers’ Field Survey, 2025

Table B indicates that the majority of respondents (49.6%) were aged 18–35 years, followed by 41.1% aged 36–55 years, and 9.3% aged 56 years and above, among the 280 participants in the study.

Table C: Religion of Respondents
Religion

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Christianity	114	40.7	40.7	40.7
	Islam	124	44.3	44.3	85.0
	Traditional African Religions	42	15.0	15.0	100.0
	Total	280	100.0	100.0	

Source: Researchers’ Field Survey, 2025

Table C shows that among the 280 respondents, 44.3% identified as Muslims, 40.7% as Christians, and 15.0% practiced Traditional African Religions.

Research Question One: What is the level of adult mental health (resilience and coping, self-esteem and self-worth, trauma and post-traumatic growth) in Ibadan North Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Level of Adult Mental Health in Ibadan North LG, Oyo State, Nigeria

Items	Strongly Agree Freq (%)	Agree Freq (%)	Disagree Freq (%)	Strongly Disagree Freq (%)	Mean
Resilience and Coping	109.5(39.1)	41.5 (14.8)	93.5 (33.4)	35.5 (12.65)	2.80
Self-Esteem and Self-Worth	185.5(66.25)	19 (6.75)	28.5 (10.2)	47 (16.8)	3.23
Trauma and Post-	172(61.4)	30.5 (10.85)	55.5 (19.8)	22 (7.85)	3.26

Traumatic
Growth

Overall Weighted Mean= 3.10

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Threshold: Mean value of ≥ 3.00 (High), 2.5-2.99 (Moderate) and < 2.50 (Low)

With an overall weighted mean of 3.10, findings in Table 1 demonstrate that Ibadan North Local Government's adult mental health is generally at a high level. Resilience and coping received a moderate score of 2.80, indicating that some adults may find it difficult to adjust to stress and challenges. In contrast, self-esteem and self-worth (3.23) and trauma and post-traumatic growth (3.26) received high scores, indicating strong personal identities and positive recovery experiences.

Research Question Two: What is the level of spirituality (spiritual practices, values and ethics, personal growth and self-reflection) among adults in Ibadan North Local Government, Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of Spirituality among Adults in Ibadan North LG, Oyo State, Nigeria

Items	Strongly Agree Freq (%)	Agree Freq (%)	Disagree Freq (%)	Strongly Disagree Freq (%)	Mean
Spiritual Practices	157(56.1)	45(16.1)	46(16.45)	32(11.45)	3.17
Values and Ethics	118.5(42.3)	38.5(13.75)	69(24.6)	54(19.3)	2.79
Personal Growth and Self-Reflection	116(41.4)	35(12.5)	91 (32.5)	38(13.6)	2.82

Overall Weighted Mean= 2.93

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Threshold: Mean value of ≥ 3.00 (High), 2.5-2.99 (Moderate) and < 2.50 (Low)

According to the results in Table 2, the overall weighted mean score of 2.93 shows that adults in Ibadan North Local Government have a moderate level of spirituality. While values and ethics (2.79) and personal growth and self-reflection (2.82) were in the moderate range, spiritual practices had the highest mean of 3.17 among the three variables evaluated, indicating a high level of engagement.

Test of Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between spirituality and adult mental health in Ibadan North local government, Oyo state, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.987 ^a	.975	.975	.937

a. Predictors: (Constant), Spirituality
Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9412.207	1	9412.207	10714.156	.000 ^b
	Residual	244.218	278	.878		
	Total	9656.425	279			

a. Dependent Variable: Adult Mental Health
b. Predictors: (Constant), Spirituality
Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	1.441	.175		8.248	.000
	Spirituality	.976	.009	.987	103.509	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Adult Mental Health
Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

The statistical findings show that among adults in Ibadan North Local Government, spirituality and mental health are highly and significantly correlated. Spirituality explains 97.5% of the variance in adult mental health, according to the correlation coefficient ($R = .987$) and the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = .975$), demonstrating an extraordinarily strong predictive association. This association is statistically significant ($F = 10,714.156$, $p = .000$), according to the ANOVA table, and the regression coefficient for spirituality ($B = .976$, $p = .000$) indicates a strong positive influence, indicating that adult mental health improves as spirituality rises.

Discussion of Findings

The finding in Table 1 implies that while the majority of the adults in the region have good mental health, positive self-esteem, and the capacity to recover from trauma, interventions that enhance coping mechanisms and resilience are necessary to guarantee comprehensive mental health.

Although adults in Ibadan North Local Government typically participate in spiritual activities at a high level, results in Table 2 suggest that their incorporation of spiritual ideals, ethics, and personal development into everyday life is only moderate. This implies that while spirituality exists, it can be more centred on rituals or practices than on ethical living or inward development, which could have an impact on how spirituality affects their mental health.

The statistical results indicate that there is a substantial and positive correlation between spirituality and adult mental health, with the null hypothesis being rejected because the p-value is less than 0.05. This suggests that spirituality is essential for improving mental health in this demographic of adults, hence bolstering the significance of spiritual aspects in mental health interventions and policy.

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, adults in Ibadan North Local Government have a high degree of mental health and a moderate level of spirituality, with spirituality both favourably influencing and significantly predicting adult mental health. This emphasises how crucial it is to incorporate spiritual elements into community-based mental health awareness and intervention initiatives.

Recommendations

In light of the results, the following recommendations are appropriate:

1. Given their beneficial effects on adult mental health, mental health practitioners ought to integrate spiritual ideals and practices into counselling and therapeutic procedures.
2. To raise awareness of the ways in which spirituality may enhance mental health, particularly via resilience-building and personal development, community and religious leaders should work with mental health advocates.
3. Particularly in metropolitan Nigerian environments like Ibadan North, government and health organisations should create culturally aware mental health initiatives that recognise the importance of spirituality.
4. To improve individuals' coping mechanisms and sense of self-worth, educational institutions, and adult learning centres should incorporate spirituality and mental health education into their outreach initiatives.

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